

Paper 12

**A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF 30 DAYS ENGLISH LANGUAGE
EMPOWERMENT OF THE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF
DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT.**

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ABSTRACT

The need for empowering teacher’s teaching English in primary schools of Karnataka gained greater significance after the national level study conducted by NCERT (2012) and ASER (2015) reveals that majority of children in government schools have not acquired of basic language skills especially reading which a foundational skill for language learning is. 30 days ELEP is one of the massive training programs taken up by the department of primary and secondary education Karnataka to train 10,200 teachers across the state with well thought objectives. The training program focuses on improving the English language proficiency as well as the English language teaching skills of in service teachers teaching at primary schools of Karnataka. A study on the Impact of 30 days English language empowerment program for the primary school teachers of Dakshina Kannada District was conducted after, training primary school teachers across Karnataka. The objectives of this study are to find out the overall impact of 30 days ELEP on the classroom transaction and overall improvement of teachers on language abilities of teachers teaching English at primary schools, status of implementation, transfer effect of training on the students learning at primary schools, improvement in teachers ability to use English, and to teach English after training. In the present study descriptive research method is used. Sample of 23% was selected for the study out of 150 teachers trained in 2016. The classroom observation data shows that no teacher achieved Excellency and 71% teachers fall under category of 60 to 85% improvement and 28% teachers’ falls under needs to improve category. After analyzing the data of students achievement test found there is no transfer effect on the language learning of students. Data of HMs reveals 80% HMs effectively implemented and 89% of parents are well aware of ELEP training.

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Key words: English Empowerment Programme (ELEP), Dakshina Kannada District, Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)

Introduction

The need for empowering teacher’s teaching English in primary schools of Karnataka gained greater significance after the national level study conducted by NCERT (2012) and ASER (2015). Regional Institute of English Bangalore has been pointed out that the quality of teaching English at primary level has not been found satisfactory in spite of introducing English from Ist standard.

Background

30 days ELEP is one of the massive training program taken up by the department of primary and secondary education to train 10,200 teachers across the state with well thought objectives. The training program focuses on improving the English language proficiency as well as these English language teaching skills of in-service teachers teaching at primary schools of Karnataka.

Objectives of the study to find out

1. overall impact of 30 days ELEP on the classroom transaction
2. impact of 30 days ELEP on the students achievement in English
3. impact of 30 days ELEP on the classroom transaction of ELEP trained teachers
4. Level of implementation of ELEP in the primary schools of Dakshina Kannada.
5. Awareness of parents about the impact of 30 days ELEP on their children.

Methodology

In the present study descriptive research method is used. Sample of 23% was selected for the study out of total population. Descriptive statistics i.e. average, mean and graphical representation namely Bar Diagram was used for the variable involved.

1.1.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table 1.1.1: Representing Number of students, Mean score and result of Achievement Test

Figure 1.1.1: Bar Diagram representing Achievement of the students in Achievement test

The mean score of the students on the students’ achievement test is 3.86. Considering the criteria

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decided during the construction of the test, it is found that there is no transfer effect of English Language 30 Days English Empowerment Programme on the students’ achievement in English. The mean score reveals that there is ample scope for improvement with regard to students’ achievements in English.

In connection to the above Figure 1.1.1, the reasons for the low transfer effect of ELEP could be,

- Lack of individual attention, exposure, interest of the students and motivations
- Lack of English speaking environment in the school and Influence of mother tongue

1.1.2 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA FROM ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING PRE AND POST TRAINING OBSERVATIONS

Part – A

- I. 1. It is observed that, 30days ELEP has been more effective on the following areas of class room interaction such as spending more time on developing the learner’s language skills, preparing and using additional learning materials, conducting activities to develop students spoken English, the teacher’s increased ability in narrating stories and involving students in pair and small group activities. The study result shows that the ability of teachers on the above mentioned areas has been improved by 17%.
2. ELEP has been more effective on the teacher’s ability and interest to use technology, additional resources and spending more time for the preparation of the class and ability of primary school teachers on the above mentioned areas has been improved by 15%.
3. The ability to involve all the learners in the classroom activities, increased level of satisfaction in teaching English has been improved by 13%.
4. The teacher’s dependency on textbook content and activities given in the textbook to transact in the classroom has been decreased by 12%and the tendency to use student’s

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mother tongue in classroom has been decreased by 13%. Student’s tendency to learn question and answers by heart has been decreased 6%.

5. The confidence level of teachers to speak English has been increased by 10% and habit of explaining the content of the lesson has been decreased by 7%.

- II. 1. It is observed that, under teaching vocabulary teacher’s ability to design additional activities to teach English has been increased by 18% and use of dictionary by the teachers and the students has been increased by 12%. The teacher’s habit of dealing with the exercises given only in the textbook has been decreased by 12% and the teacher’s tendency to write words on the blackboard and their meanings in their mother tongue has been decreased by 8.7%.
2. The teachers habit of explaining the rules of grammar and ask the students to do the exercises has been decreased for 4%. This indicates that this training has medium impact on the teacher’s habit of explaining the rules of grammar instead of teaching grammar in meaningful context and situations.
4. Under developing speaking skills there is only 1% decrease in teachers talk in the classroom which is expected to be decreased maximum. There is 14% increase in teacher-student and peer group interaction and there is 16% increase in involvement of students in different activities.
5. Under developing reading skills the result shows that there is minimum increase in teacher’s model reading in the classroom. The result also indicates there is increase in student’s involvement in louder reading and silent reading and also pair and group reading activities.
6. Under teaching writing, there is considerable increase in teacher’s involvement and interest in conducting simple writing activities and giving practice in 3 stages of writing to enhance students writing ability. There is considerable decrease in teachers emphasise on writing only question and answers and copy writing after 30 days English Language Empowerment Programme.
7. The teacher’s ability to assess the learners has been increased by 14%. They have changed their method of assessment to oral test, story narration, projects along with written assessment. The teachers’ emphasis on examination oriented teaching and written assessment has been decreased considerably.

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- III. 1. The study revealed that after 30 days ELEP teachers adopted innovative practices to improve their classroom interaction. Most of the teachers involve their students in role play, story narration, and dialogue practice to enhance their communicative skill and various writing activities such as letter writing, paragraph writing to improve the writing ability of their students.
- IV. In this tool the researcher studied the teachers Ability to use English before and after the training using 10 point scale.

1.1.2 (a) Table representing the teachers Ability to use English before and after the training in percentage

Number of teachers	Ability to use English before the training in %.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
35	-	-	3	23	34	20	6	11	-	-
Number of teachers	Ability to use English after the training in %									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
35	-	-	-	-	-	18	20	49	20	3

1.1.2 (a) Graphical representation of the teachers Ability to use English after the training

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1.1.2(b) Graphical representation of the teachers Ability to use English before the training

Ability to use English After

From the scores given by the teachers to use English before the training in a 10 point scale shows that, there are 3% of teachers falls in 3 point, 23% of teachers falls in 4 point, 35% teachers falls in 5 point, 20% teachers falls in 6 point, 6% teachers falls in 7 point, 11% teachers falls in 8 point,

The same table shows the data of teachers ability to use English after the training in a 10 point scale are 18% of teachers falls in 6 point, 20% of teachers falls in 7 point, 49% teachers falls in 8 point, 20% teachers falls in 9 point, 3% teachers falls in 10 point. This indicates that there is a considerable improvement in the ability to use English language among primary school teachers of Dakshina Kannada District.

1.1.3(a) Table representing the teachers Ability to teach English before and after the training in percentage

Number of teachers	Ability to teach English before the training in %.									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
35	-	-	3	24	14	34	14	14	-	-
Number of teachers	Ability to teach English after the training in %									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
35	-	-	-	-	-	3	20	34	34	3

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1.1.3 (a) Graphical representation of the teachers Ability to teach English before the training

Ability to teach English before training -10 point

1.1.3(b) Graphical representation of the teachers Ability to teach English after the training

Ability to teach English after training -10 point

PART – B

1. It was found that nothing major work was adopted by the teachers for their professional development after 30 days ELEP Training.

From the scores given by the teachers to teach English before the training in a 10 point scale shows that, there are 3% of teachers falls in 3 point, 20% of teachers falls in 4 point, 14% teachers falls in 5 point, 34% teachers falls in 6 point, 14% teachers falls in 7 point, 14% teachers falls in 8 point, The same table shows the data of teacher's ability to teach English after the training in a 10 point scale are 3% of teachers falls in 6 point, 20% of teachers falls in 7 point, 34% teachers falls in 8 point, 34% teachers falls in 9 point, 3% teachers falls in 10 point. This indicates that there is a considerable progress in the ability to teach English language among primary school

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teachers of Dakshina Kannada District.

Most of the teachers have the opinion that teaching poetry and grammar is difficult to them. Most of the children who studies in urban government primary schools are migrated children. Irregularity of these students is another major hindrance for better performance in English.

1.1.4 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA BY OBSERVATION SCHEDULE

Figure1.1.3 Bar Diagram representing Observation Schedule

From the figure 1.1.3 it is revealed that Analysing the data collected from the observation schedule and considering criteria decided during the preparation of observation schedule, it was observed that no teacher achieved Excellency level by scoring above 85%. 25 out of 35 teachers (71%) have reached 60 to 85% and where good categorised under the grade. 10 teachers (28%) scored less than 60 % and grouped under ‘needs improvement’ category.

Figure 1.1.4: Bar Diagram representing components of Observation Schedule

It was observed that 74% of the teachers were able to use teachers talk very effectively in their

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classroom. 57% of students were able to communicate well in English. It was found that 60% of teachers were able to use innovative strategies in their classes. 67% of the teachers could manage their classes very well and 67% of teachers could evaluate students understanding very well.

1.1.4 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA BY HM

Table 1.1.4 Representing data by HMs

above 85	18	very effective
80 to 85	13	effective
below 80	4	needs improvement

Figure 1.1.4: Bar Diagram representing the data by HM

Analysing the data collected from the checklist provided to HMs, it is found that 51.42% of the HMs opined 85% of implementation, 37.14% of the Head Masters assured that 80% of implementation and rest of the HMs implementation stood below 80%. The data reveals that most of the headmasters are successful in effective implementation of ELEP in their respective schools.

1.1.5 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIO OF DATA BY PARENTS

Table: 1.1.5 Representing data by parents

above 85	119	very effective
80 to 85	18	effective
below 80	38	needs improvement

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Figure 1.1.5: Bar Diagram representing the data by Parents

As per the analysis of the data collected from the parents 89% of the parents are well aware of effective implementation of ELEP in the schools. Remaining 11 % of the parents, some of them were completely unaware, some were ignorant to the happenings of schools and few of them don't understand all these.

Conclusion: Parents and HMs have given positive feedback on ELEP. When researcher went through data collected from student's achievement test and teachers observation found that no teacher has reached excellent level. 51% of teachers are on the satisfactory teaching level. Most of the teachers lag in the use of technology in their classes despite the emphasis laid on it during the 30 days training.
